

8T – Dark Matter is a Must

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T and in particular the second variation of the main equation, it is possible to expand the idea which was analyzed before, using variational distributions of matter. It is possible to explain why dark matter is a direct result of the 8T construction using the condition of stationarity.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2A) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.41)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We can represent the second variation of the main equation as the following

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_m - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_n = 0 \quad (2.1.B)$$

That construction is the following. Each manifold has area of extremum curvatures on it. Those extremum curvatures are surrounded by arbitrary variations, which vanished into matter. Up to this point, it was covered. For each arbitrary amount of variation absorbed onto the $\partial g / \partial t$ there is a radiation emitted from the area of extremum curvature to ensure it does not vary over time. those galaxies than has areas of extremum curvatures, and arbitrary variations around them, that is matter clusters, spiraling around those areas. The galaxy as an area of extremum curvature is getting flattened by another galaxy of the same magnitude and different matter distribution. As was previously analyzed:

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \delta g_i \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^{s_1} \in [0,1]$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \delta g_i \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^{s_2} \in [0,1]$$

$$\mathcal{R}^{s_1} \neq \mathcal{R}^{s_2}$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \delta g_i \equiv \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \delta g_i$$

The key point of this paper which was not presented before is the following – if we require the manifold to have areas of extremum curvatures and time invariant acceleration away from those areas, than by (2.1.B) we also require a set of arbitrary variations vanishing onto matter, around the matter of our own galaxy. The amount is the same, the distribution is different, invisible matter is also an immediate result of the main equation. Now take an infinite set of manifolds in the packet and the matter within one distinct manifold is now at the position of a minority as it is only belong to one manifold. Not only the main equation represent matter formation in our manifold, it also represent matter creation in other manifolds. While areas of extremum curvature flattening each other, matter is constantly being created in different distribuends across all manifolds, and as a result accounts for what is speculated as invisible matter. It could be explain that way, that the areas of extremum curvature alone with the matter distribution of one distinct manifold is not sufficient for holding the condition $\partial g / \partial t = 0$. However, an infinite set of pairs forming the packet is sufficient. That means that in order for the stationarity condition of the manifold to hold, one must have at least two distributions of arbitrary variations vanishing onto matter, in different configurations. Dark matter than is a must and is just regular matter signature of a distinct manifolds. that matter is creating the additional gravitational effect ensuring the $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ condition of stationarity. The formation of matter than can be described by the Quark masses series, which indicate nature is devising in increasing amount to eliminate those arbitrary variations. with the arrow of time, families with total mass which is lighter and lighter is formed but the structure of the families is the same, i.e. two distinct elements which differ in sign and create threefold combinations. Put another way the main equations describe an infinite distinct sets of matter creations, and the Quark masses series indicate their total mass direction, assumed same for all.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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